

Depln-O: Catalog of Concepts

Term	Definition
Dependency	An OOC-O Class that is associated with an Injector through a Dependency Injection.
Consumer	An OOC-O Class that possesses at least one Injector as a component.
Injector	An OOC-O Instance Method or an OOC-O Instance Variable that is associated with a Dependency through a Dependency Injection.
Dependency Injection	The injection of a Dependency through an Injector in a Consumer.
Method Injector	A non-Constructor OOC-O Instance Method that is an Injector.
Constructor Injector	An OOC-O Constructor Method that is an Injector.
Property Injector	An OOC-O Instance Variable that is an Injector.
Abstract Dependency	An OOC-O Abstract Class that is a Dependency.
Concrete Dependency	An OOC-O Concrete Class that is a Dependency.
Dependency Implementation	A Concrete Dependency that is an implementation of an Abstract Dependency
Primary Dependency	The Dependency Implementation invoked to resolve the Abstract Dependency by default.
Qualified Dependency	A Dependency Implementation invoked to satisfy the Dependency when called with a specific parameter or under a specific configuration.
Dependency Specification	The parameter or configuration that specifies what Dependency Implementation will be invoked to resolve the Abstract Dependency (The lack of Dependency Specification means invoking the Primary Dependency)
Decorator	A class that is both a Dependency Implementation and a Consumer of the same Abstract Dependency (its Injector invokes a different implementation of the Dependency)
Singleton Dependency	A Concrete Dependency with a scope that determines that only one instance of it will be created for the application.
Dependent Dependency	A Concrete Dependency with a scope that determines a new instance of it will be created for each consumer.
Web Scoped Depedency	A Concrete Dependency with a scope that is defined in the context of a Web application.

Request Scoped Dependency	A Concrete Dependency with a scope that determines that a new instance of the Concrete Dependency will be created for every new HTTP request.
Session Scoped Dependency	A Concrete Dependency with a scope that determines that a new instance of it will be created for every new HTTP session, but the same instance will be maintained throughout the session.
Application Scoped Dependency	A Concrete Dependency with a scope that determines that only one instance of it will exist for the entirety of the Web application.